

7 October 2021

Cape Town,
South Africa

Email: daowusu-agyekum@parliament.gh

Re: **Open Letter to Parliament in Opposition to the Promotion of Proper Human Sexual Rights and Ghanaian Family Values Bill 2021**

Blessings and warmest greetings to my dear sisters and brothers in Ghana. We write am writing to you both in as devoted sisters in Christ and as ordained leaders in the Christian Church.

Our father, Archbishop Emeritus Desmond Tutu has often said that he would not serve a homophobic God, and this Bill causes us to affirm this statement. We have searched the Bill, high and low, for signs of God. And we regret that we cannot find a single word that testifies to the love of God in this Bill.

Our prayer is that Ghana, the beacon of freedom and justice for Africa and its diaspora, can avoid South Africa's horrific history of apartheid and firmly reject this Bill which seeks to create a gay apartheid in Ghana to victimize our very own children and imperil our future.

And for what?

LGBTQ+ people are not cancers to be excised from the Ghanaian family. They are us, and we are them, all of us mere humans, together forming an inextricable part of the bloodline that is our African family. We can seek to destroy sexual and gender minorities in windowless cells, or scatter them to the four corners of the earth, and we will fail because, no matter what, we are them and they are us. We speak here of our family. We are forever one.

Every member of our beloved family is sacred and equal before God. My prayer is that we will strive to be more understanding and compassionate toward all God's children so that we can glean God's purpose for their lives and our own.

It is only together that we can build a country and a continent worthy of the many, many gifts with which we have been blessed. All our children are gifts with whom God blesses us. We may neither understand nor always agree with them, the Bible teaches us to lean not on our own understanding but rather to trust God, God's Word and God's divine plan. We must not criminalise our children for being as God has created them to be.

Therefore, to our leaders in Parliament, to our cultural custodians, to our fellow servants in faith, our appeal to you is simple: please reject this Bill in its entirety.

Love and protect do not disparage or jail, the minorities, sexual or otherwise, among us.

Love and protect, do not judge and disdain our family members, lest we ourselves be judged.

It is love, coupled with peace and compassion, that will protect and serve the Ghanaian family.

We stand with God and with you for good. This is why we must all unite to emphatically reject this Bill, as it fails at its core, to embody the greatest attribute of God, and teaching of Christ, which we all know is love.

Yours in love forever,

The Rev. Dr N T [REDACTED] & The Rev C [REDACTED] M T [REDACTED] [REDACTED] F [REDACTED]